

THE CONTRIBUTION OF FEMALE SINGERS FROM THE FERGANA VALLEY TO MUSIC CULTURE

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the vocal styles of female singers from the Fergana Valley. It explores their contributions to music, focusing on the integration of national traditions and modern technologies. The study discusses the musical schools in the Fergana Valley, traditional maqoms, folk songs, and their performance styles. Furthermore, it examines the emotional aspects of the singers' performances, vocal techniques, stage movements, communication skills, and the role of musical instrumentation. This research aims to investigate the cultural, pedagogical, and creative factors influencing the development of female singers' performance styles.*

Keywords: *female singers, Fergana Valley, vocal style, national traditions, maqom, folk songs, vocal technique, stage movements, musical instruments, modern technologies, lyrical performance, improvisation.*

Introduction. The improvement of female singers' performance styles is of great importance not only in their professional development but also in the advancement of Uzbek music. Deeply understanding the meaning of each song and effectively conveying its emotional aspects to the listener plays a crucial role in enhancing the singer's performance. Unveiling the inner meaning of every word and melody in the song contributes significantly to the perfection of the singer's execution. For this purpose, it is essential for the singer to enrich the song's meaning with their own emotional experience.

Materials and Methods. The improvement of performance styles among female singers plays a crucial role not only in their professional development but also in the overall advancement of Uzbek musical art. A deep understanding of the content of each song and the ability to convey its emotional aspects effectively to the audience is vital in enhancing a singer's performance. The ability to reveal the internal meaning of every word and melody in a song significantly contributes to perfecting the singer's interpretation. To achieve this, it is necessary for the singer to enrich the song's content with their own emotional experience.

In modern practice, advanced technologies are widely used to analyze and improve voice characteristics. For instance, audio analysis software such as "Praat" is used to measure voice timbre, range, and stability. These programs play an essential role in monitoring and enhancing the quality of a singer's voice, as well as providing significant assistance in identifying the necessary directions for further development [1].

Studying the musical schools of the Fergana Valley and their traditions is an important source for female singers. Mastering national maqoms, folk songs, and their performance styles helps singers introduce new approaches to their own performances. Additionally, expanding the repertoire and paying special attention to classical songs and traditional music enhances the singer's experience and skill.

Furthermore, “stage movements, facial expressions, and communication skills are of significant importance in the performance process. Planning stage movements and establishing emotional connection with the audience further enhances the singer's creative mastery” [2]. The process of improving female singers' performance styles requires the integration of national traditions with modern technologies. This harmony serves to enrich the musical heritage and continue the development of Uzbek musical art. “The use of modern styles and technologies, while simultaneously preserving traditional performance styles, ensures the development and perfection of this art form” [3].

Results and discussions. From the past to the present day, the musical life of the Fergana Valley has developed in connection with performance and creative arts. In particular, musical folklore examples have been widely spread in the districts surrounding the valley, forming and spreading in connection with past rituals and holidays. Starting from the 20th century, music folklore has developed in a new cultural and spiritual system, in the direction of artistic amateurism. In addition to folklore examples, classical music genres began to take shape in the region from the late Middle Ages, including classical singing methods, grand songs, maqom, and epic storytelling arts.

The art of maqom, which became an integral part of cultural life, particularly the Shashmaqom, Fergana-Tashkent maqom styles, has been mastered by singers and musicians, and later by amateur maqom ensembles, during the 19th and 20th centuries. During this period, maqom art developed and shaped as a central element of music culture and expanded on a large scale. Maqom art was not only a musical creation but also held great importance in social life. Distinct maqom schools formed in different regions, each with its unique characteristics.

Today, Fergana-Tashkent maqom styles are taught in the musical education system, and performance traditions are preserved. Research into these maqom styles by maqom performers and musicologists, and their teaching to the new generation, is promoting the richness of national culture. The Fergana-Tashkent maqom styles play a significant role not only in Uzbekistan but also internationally in showcasing the uniqueness and rich heritage of our national music.

Looking at folk music in performance traditions, it is clear that from cradle to grave, folk music has been enriched with unique traditions throughout its existence. The lifestyle and culture of the Uzbek people have been reflected through musical creation for centuries. Specifically, today in Uzbekistan, songs, yalla, grand songs, epic stories, instrumental tunes, and maqoms are considered mature genres of Uzbek classical music. These musical genres are part of the immense spiritual heritage created by our people and hold great significance as part of Uzbek culture and values.

According to sources, Uzbek professional (master) art was formed and developed in the early centuries of the common era. The roots of this art trace back to examples of folk music creation. “Uzbek classical music was formed on the basis of folk music and through the development of performance culture. Later, this process harmonized with Eastern classical poetry and music, sparking the emergence of new genres and styles. The foundation of classical music was the rich musical culture of the people, and the creative works of musicians and composers” [4]. Specifically, songs and instrumental music were considered the main means of expressing the spiritual-aesthetic values of the Uzbek people.

Classical music refers to musical art created by the people of Uzbekistan, over centuries, by its outstanding musicians and composers. Among these, songs, yalla, maqom, and instrumental

music hold a special place. Through the performance of these genres, not only musical skill but also performance culture and national values have been passed down from generation to generation. Moreover, the mutual relationship between folk music and classical music becomes a key factor in the development of performance traditions.

The performance styles of female singers in the Fergana Valley have a unique and rich history. In this region, female singers have developed a wide range of performance styles, from traditional music to modern performance techniques. Female singers in the Fergana Valley showcase their skills in performing traditional folk music, particularly maqom and folk songs. For example, Uzbekistan People's Artist Zamira Suyunova, Uzbekistan People's Artist and recipient of the "For Great Services" order Munojot Yo'lchieva, Uzbekistan and Tajikistan People's Artist Matluba Dadaboeva, Uzbekistan People's Artist Yorqinoy Khotamova, Uzbekistan People's Artist Golsanam Mamazoitova, Uzbekistan Honored Artist Komila Aminova, Nodira Pirmatova, Mavluda Boymatova, and Dildora Kamolova, among others, express maqoms perfectly in their performances, striving to preserve folk traditions and culture. They participate in numerous national holidays and cultural events, showcasing their performances.

The process of improving performance styles requires cultural, pedagogical, and creative approaches. From a pedagogical perspective, preparing students, especially young singers, for lyrical performance and expressive artistry is of great importance. Teachers and mentors must pay attention not only to technical aspects but also to the psychological and emotional states of the singers. Another important aspect of performance styles is intonation and richness of variations. Each singer selects intonation according to the capabilities of their voice, creating uniqueness in their performance. This opportunity allows female singers to demonstrate various improvisations in their performances. In the modern era, new forms of traditional music are developing. By adding new musical arrangements and incorporating pop elements into traditional songs, their popularity among listeners is increasing. However, it is important to ensure that traditional rules are not violated in this process.

The performance art of female singers initially developed as an amateur tradition. They mainly performed at family gatherings, local meetings, and folk festivals. In these processes, the unique features of local culture have been preserved. Modern singers, however, perform on professional stages, striving to enrich traditional music with modern elements. For example, traditional songs and maqoms are being integrated with pop music styles. In the performances of female singers, the technique of soft and gentle voice is of great importance. This technique not only demonstrates the natural beauty of the voice but also conveys the essence of the music to the listener's heart. Breathing exercises, particularly controlling the voice through the diaphragm, are a key aspect of vocal training for singers in this region.

The use of local musical instruments is an inseparable part of Fergana Valley music. Instruments such as the tanbur, dutar, qoshnay, and doira accompany the songs and enrich the aesthetic structure of the performance. These musical traditions have primarily developed through local folk songs, and the themes of the songs are usually devoted to love, nature, and human relationships. The lyrics of the songs are often taken from classical literature, particularly the poetic heritage of Alisher Navoi, Babur, Furqat, and other classical poets.

The music schools in the Fergana Valley, including the famous "Shashmaqom" traditional music school, have had a significant influence on the performance styles of female singers. The techniques and mastery from these schools are clearly reflected in the performances of female

singers. These singers are especially known for their proficiency in performing maqom and folk songs. They strive to preserve the subtlety and elegance of maqoms while also incorporating new creative elements into their performances. Each region has its own unique cultural traditions. Female singers in the Fergana Valley have added elements of local traditions, songs, and dances to their performance styles, making their performances even more appealing. The Fergana-Tashkent maqom routes are a distinctive musical style that has developed based on Eastern musical traditions and is one of Uzbekistan's rich heritage maqom routes. The formation and development of these maqoms are based on the cultural environment of the Fergana Valley and Tashkent regions.

The Fergana-Tashkent maqoms are distinguished by their complex structure, refined rhythmic techniques, and the rich meaning of the melodic movements. In these maqoms, the use of doira (a type of drum) techniques plays a key role, offering rich rhythmic possibilities that control the inner dynamics of the melody. These techniques encompass a wide range of patterns, from simple methods to complex rhythmic structures, reflecting the uniqueness of each section and movement. For example, sections like “Ufar” stand out with their lively and fast rhythms, while sections like “Nasr” and “Bayot” require slower, calmer techniques. Each doira technique gives the melody its own distinct character and emotional state, allowing the listener to feel the meaning of the melody more deeply. The rhythmic structure of the Fergana-Tashkent maqoms is complex and rich, playing an important role in revealing the emotional and dramatic essence of the music. These maqoms often feature complex time signatures such as 6/8 and 10/8, with the main beats defined by the doira and other instruments. The rhythmic patterns enhance the emotional meaning of the maqoms and serve to alter the listener's feelings. The melodic movements reflect national identity and musical diversity. The melodies begin slowly and simply, gradually becoming more complex, adding dramatic depth to the music.

Repeated motifs and transitions between different tonalities ensure the multilayered and intricate structure of the maqom, offering wide opportunities for creativity for the singer or instrumentalist. Fergana-Tashkent maqoms primarily consist of ashula (folk songs), with instrumental routes appearing less frequently. Their distinctiveness lies in the integration of epic poetry, folk songs, and classical poetry. The Fergana-Tashkent maqom routes include four main categories: Bayot, Dugohi Husayniy, Chorgoh, and Shahnozi Gulyor. Each of these categories is divided into six sections, named in forms such as “Bayot I-VI” and “Chorgoh I-VI”. The Fergana-Tashkent maqom routes are based on the Shashmaqom routes, but they are distinguished by local features in their performance style. For instance, while the “Bayot”, “Dugoh-Husayniy” and “Chorgoh” routes originate from the same sections of Shashmaqom, their melodic structure and doira techniques are somewhat simplified. The Shahnozi Gulyor route emerged from various maqom sections. In these maqoms, great importance is placed on the meaning of the poetry and the rhythmic structure. Often, rubaiyat, ghazals, or fard from classical poets are sung in the maqom melodies. The harmony between the poem and the melody gives the listener a high level of aesthetic pleasure.

In the Fergana Valley, performers have creatively used folk instruments and vocal techniques to create new musical forms. Maqom theory has been deeply studied in singing centers, and performance traditions have been developed. In these schools, music education is integrated with both religious and secular knowledge. During the time of Amir Timur and the Timurid dynasty, maqom art became an integral part of court culture. Court musicians created new

interpretations of maqoms, elevating their artistic level. The musical cultures of Central Asian regions harmonized, and maqom art flourished. The synthesis of various national musical traditions turned maqom art into a shared cultural value. Together with the Fergana Valley, Tashkent is often referred to as part of the Fergana-Tashkent local style. This is because the music culture and classical music examples, music language, and performance styles of Fergana and Tashkent regions are very similar.

By interpreting the meaning of the melody from the performer's perspective, the emotional impact of the maqoms is intensified. The performance schools that formed in the Fergana Valley have not only contributed to regional culture but also played an invaluable role in the rise of national culture. Especially, female singers have played a vital role in preserving traditional music, developing the art of music, and passing it on to the next generations through their performances. Studying performance styles in the history of music is of great importance. Specifically, the singing skills of performers and their unique approach to interpreting melodies and songs help identify the development dynamics of musical culture. For example, the structural components of "Bayot 1" and "Nasri Bayot" from the "Bayot" school—small structures like phrases—are linked to the climax of the melody, forming the essential building blocks of musical development.

In "Nasri Bayot", the climax covers a broad range and includes rhythmic and melodic connections between phrases. These connections ensure the richness of rhythm, tonality, and intonation. Especially in the performances of female singers, these connections are enriched with emotions, deepening the meaning of the music and enhancing its aesthetic value. The melody and intonational characteristics of each phrase enable the singer to blend more deeply with the musical meaning. The singer focuses not only on the technical aspects of musical expression but also on infusing their performance with individual style and deep emotion, thus bringing the piece to life.

The performance styles of maqom singing is a distinct topic, and specialists in this field have conducted specific studies. The performance style, especially the issue of "shayla" in maqom performances, is an important aspect. "Shayla" is a term in music that expresses the performance style, particularly in maqom singing and vocal performance. Shayla plays a significant role in expressing the characteristics of the music, specifically in conveying the performance method and a certain musical path. This term includes the stylistic approaches of music in different regions or by different performers, particularly vocal delivery, tempo, and formal performance techniques.

"In Bukhara and Samarkand, the performance of maqom routes is often carried out in a style unique to the local dialect, which might not be immediately appealing to someone who has heard or learned the same melodies performed in a different dialect. For example, when the famous singer Domla Halim Ibodov came to Tashkent in 1937, this situation occurred. At first, the listeners did not fully appreciate his high level of skill in maqom performance and his extraordinary, distinctive style of singing. However, over time, thousands of fans in Tashkent and the Fergana Valley came to admire his talent. With his broad vocal range and pleasant voice, he won the hearts of the listeners and made maqom routes beloved by many" [5].

The performance styles of female singers from the Fergana Valley hold a special place in Uzbekistan's rich musical culture. Their artistry serves as a unique bridge in preserving, developing, and advancing national music traditions. The women singers of this region stand out not only for their voices and performance skills but also for their deep musical knowledge and contribution to promoting national values. For example, the famous singer Yoqubbekov Sabohatkhon made a significant contribution to promoting the maqom traditions of the Fergana

Valley. She performed the most difficult and complex variants of the Fergana-Tashkent maqom paths, adapting them to her voice. She elevated the primary task of maqom—expressing the emotions of music—to a high level. In this, her style reflects the harmonious blend of “chavandozlik” (horseman-style) and “qoshikchilik” (singer-style).

The “chavandozlik” style stands out in Uzbek music art, especially in maqom performance, as a unique and distinctive style. This style not only reflects the artistic expressiveness of music but also fully captures its spiritual and aesthetic aspects. The “chavandozlik” style particularly deepens the connection between the singer and the music, ensuring harmony between high technical skill, traditional features, and performance style in the execution of musical material.

The uniqueness of the style lies in harmonizing the links between the voice and music, allowing for a complete expression of the music's emotional and spiritual aspects. In the Fergana-Tashkent maqom traditions, the “chavandozlik” style is especially widespread due to the fusion of modern and traditional performance techniques. In this style, the singer demonstrates mastery in accurately expressing all the subtleties and repetitions of the maqom [6]. The voice of Bunda Khonanda, with its richness and the style of performance, creates a perfect harmony with the music itself, giving each melody and song a new meaning and depth. It is this unique style that elevates the maqom art of the Fergana Valley and Tashkent to the highest levels.

Sabohatkhon's performance places great importance on the embellishments of the melody. She deeply feels the subtle changes in the maqom paths and the unique characteristics of each tone. Sabohatkhon's ability to express the embellishments and melodic lines correctly, as well as the dynamics—i.e., the soft (light) and forte (strong) phases—are clearly articulated in her performance. She successfully reflects the words of the songs and their spiritual meaning in her voice. The singer has mastered many aspects of maqom performance techniques. She not only maintains perfect control over high notes, but she also produces strong and clear low notes. When performing the Fergana-Tashkent maqom paths, Sabohatkhon does not limit herself to traditional styles but also refreshes the maqoms with modern interpretations, enriching her performances. She utilizes her improvisational skills and, at times, adapts the maqoms in her unique way, ensuring her performances are fresh. This approach to performance reflects her creative thinking and adds a new breath to the music.

Furthermore, the work of the renowned singer Saodat Sodiqova is also recognized as a bright example of the musical culture of the Fergana Valley. Her performance style is deeply connected to the musical traditions of the Fergana Valley, with her voice standing out due to its unique softness and deep emotional resonance. In her performance, Saodat Sodiqova blends traditional methods with modern elements, breathing new life into folk songs. She feels the spirit of national melodies deeply, drawing the listener into the inner world of music. Without disrupting the traditional structure of folk songs, she gives them a modern voice, successfully attracting the younger generation to national music. This demonstrates her openness to creative experiments. Her vocal timbre reflects the spirit of Uzbek folk music with its resonance. Through her high technical mastery, particularly her control over breathing, tonality, and dynamics, she gives a unique expression to the songs.

Through her heartfelt singing of songs like “Shahzoda,” “Muhabbatimsan,” “Bahor Keldi,” “Dugonajon,” “Yurak Yig‘lar,” and “O‘zbeqim,” she expresses love and loyalty, the beauty of spring, joy in the human heart, friendship, and sincerity through national melodies. Her performances combine lyrical tonality with dramatic power, allowing the listener not only to hear

but also to feel each song. This style sets her apart from other singers. Saodat Sodiqova's performance style is significant not only in preserving traditions but also in developing them and passing them on to new generations. Her performances are aimed at revealing the delicacy and deep philosophical meaning of national music. In songs like "Munojot," "Segoh Maqomi," and "Bozori Qand," special attention is paid to harmonizing the tonality with the content of the lyrics. She has a unique experience in delicately expressing the complex musical phrases that are harmonized with the classical sounds of the maqom.

Oydin Tojiyeva has demonstrated a unique delicacy and emotional depth in performing maqom art and folk songs. In her performances, respect for folk traditions and modern interpretations blend harmoniously. She skillfully sings songs such as "Doston", "Ushshoq Maqomi" and "Dilhiroj". In her performance, the classical styles of folk music and maqom art merge with contemporary melodies. She performs folk songs with a distinctive tonality and simple emotional harmony. Her performance style is refined and sincere, capturing the listener with deep emotions. Many female singers from the valley have shown their mastery in performing widely popular maqom paths like "Munojot", "Girya" and "Segoh" among the people. During their performances of these paths, they not only use traditional methods but also enrich the meaning of the musical compositions through their unique creative approach. "For example, in the performance of the 'Girya' path, the elasticity of the voice and the expression of spiritual strength play a particularly important role" [7].

The performance styles of female singers from the Fergana Valley stand out with their rich history and unique characteristics. These singers have demonstrated great skill not only in performing traditional maqom and folk songs but also in modern pop music genres. In their performances, the harmony of grace, expressiveness, and stylistic beauty, as well as special attention to vocal techniques and breathing, ensure their professional development. The perfection of their performances is important not only for the development of art but also for understanding national identity, preserving cultural heritage, and passing it on to future generations. Today, the process of controlling and improving singers' voices with the help of modern technologies, such as audio analysis programs, has become more effective. Analysis and Discussion The innovations in the performance styles of female singers from the Fergana Valley are mainly based on blending traditional music with modern forms. Additionally, the individual characteristics of the performance style, particularly the importance of the *shayla* (a key term in the performance of maqom and folk music), are emphasized. *Shayla* represents a key term that reflects the unique characteristics of the performance style in maqom singing and folk music. The distinctiveness of the maqom and folk music performance styles formed in the Fergana Valley is related to their rich rhythmic structures, lyrical approaches, and the complexity of the music's mechanics. All these factors are crucial in elevating the vocal skills of female singers to a high level.

Analysis and Discussion. The distinctive feature of music in the Fergana Valley is its expression in various forms. Specifically, maqom, mug'om, folk music, folk songs, and various programs hold significant places in this region. Female singers, by performing these musical forms, not only focus on their technical aspects but also ensure the emotional and spiritual transmission of the music. Through their performances, female singers convey the deep meaning and content of the music to the listener.

The contribution of female singers to music is manifested in two main areas. Firstly, they make a significant contribution to the preservation of traditional music. Secondly, they participate

in the development of modern musical forms. Female singers, especially in preserving the styles of traditional music such as maqom and folk music, have also succeeded in introducing new forms and innovations in music. This, in turn, ensures that music reaches new generations.

The contribution of female singers from the valley shows that they play an important role not only in preserving traditional music forms but also in its renewal and development. Their high skill in performance, naturalness in expressing emotions through music, and loyalty to authenticity also prove effective in creating new forms of music. In this way, female singers are an integral part of the music culture of the Fergana Valley and play an essential role in shaping its future.

Conclusion. The contribution of female singers from the Fergana Valley to music culture is unparalleled. They blend modern and traditional forms of music, helping to preserve the richness of folk music. In addition to ensuring the aesthetic beauty and spiritual content of music, their performances have become a source of inspiration for the new generation. Despite the conservative views and gender stereotypes in society, which may pose obstacles for female singers, they continue to resist these barriers and persist in their creative activities. The contribution of female singers from Fergana not only serves the development of Uzbek music but also helps shape the future of national music as a whole.

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